

Measuring Experience in Information Design

Emotional Responses to Medical Decision Aids based on Demographic Groups

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Abstract: Information design elements such as colors, shapes, diagrams, and visual imagery affect how people perceive information. Medical decision aids (DAs) are designed to help patients understand their options when they discuss medical situations with medical providers. This research explores which information design elements affect people's emotions. It examines ways to measure people's emotion with regard to the information graphics used in medical DA across a variety of demographic groups. As a research method, focus group studies and a survey were conducted with emotional property words. Qualitative and quantitative data was collected and analyzed to measure the emotional and experience related properties of the DAs. This research found that gender, age, income, and education levels affect the perception of information graphics used in medical DAs.

Key words: *Measuring Emotion, Information Design, Diverse Groups, Medical Decision Aids, Emotional Property Words.*

1. Introduction

DAs are tools that assist patients by helping them understand their options and consider their personal preferences with regard to the impact of benefits and harm in making specific medical decisions [1, 2]. The Cochrane Collaboration review, *Decision Aids for People Facing Health Treatment or Screening Decisions*, has noted that the use of decision aids compared to typical healthcare measures help people feel more comfortable with their decisions. Patients who use DAs, says Cochrane, score lower on decision conflict scales thus indicating a greater comfort level with their decisions. These patients tend to feel more well informed about their treatment options and make decisions that are more closely aligned with their personal values [3]. In addition, evidence suggests that patients who are involved in the treatment decision-making process are less likely to suffer over their choices and do better with regard to their treatments [4]. According to Coulter and Entwistle [5], people did not prefer any specific type of media delivery (web sites, questionnaires, brochures, etc.); however there may be preferences with regard to the type or style of the content. These researchers found that people preferred structured and concise materials that included pictures and diagrams.

This research focuses on how visual information in the context of medical decision aids (DAs) affects human experience. The objectives of this research are to discuss user responses and perceptions of visual information used in a specific DA for the purpose of making complex medical decisions with regard to type 2 diabetes.

The Ottawa Hospital Research Institute (OHRI) at the Ottawa Hospital and the University of Ottawa has developed an extensive set of guidelines for measuring and evaluating DAs. Founded in 1995, the Patient Decision Aid research group at Ottawa helps patients and medical providers make difficult healthcare decisions through DA-guided discussions. The Ottawa Health Decision Centre has set policies for the design and evaluation of DAs such as choice predisposition/decision, decision conflict scale, regret, stage of decision making, acceptability, knowledge, realistic expectations, values, preparation for decision making, and decision self efficacy [6].

Even though there are many guidelines, the quality of decision aids varies greatly and there are still debates with regard to the underlying concepts for creating decision aids. There is still an overall lack of agreement about the criteria for developing DAs. In addition, there are no clear guidelines for the visual design of the visual information in the DAs or their emotional properties. Therefore there is a need to establish an understanding of the role of visual information design and its emotional properties with regard to a wide range of demographic user groups.

This research examined various user groups with regard to their emotional responses to DAs. The research was specifically looking for differences or similarities based on demographic groups. The following questions were examined:

Do different genders show similar emotional responses to the DAs?

Do different age groups show similar emotional responses to the DAs? and

Do different income groups show similar emotional responses to the DAs?

2. Research Methods

Six cards as designed by the Knowledge and Encounter Research (KER) Unit and the SPARC Innovation Program at the Mayo Clinic were used in this research (Figure 1). These cards were collaboratively developed to successfully facilitate consultations between patients and physicians [7].

2.1. Visual Analysis of DA Cards

The size of the cards is an outer dimension of 5" x 9 ¼" with rounded corners and a white background. Each card has a 1 inch top bar. The top bars are each a different color with a one or two line title written in either black or white text. The font used is Franklin Gothic with the headlines of the five treatment categories in bold. Bold weight text is also used for emphasis on certain words in the body copy of card 6. The title on each card is 36 point type with sub-heads in 18 point type. The body copy for each card is 14 point or lower in a normal weight font. A heavy plastic lamination is applied to each card with matte on the front side and gloss on the back of the each card. The top line of text is 3/8" below the color bar; however, the side and bottom margins are not consistent between cards. All six cards use the same five treatment categories in the same top to bottom order as sub-headings on the cards. Card 1 and card 6 use only typography in their design. Card 1 has the least amount of text of any of the cards. The text has only the names of the five treatment categories with a number or range to indicate the percentage of A1c reduction. The text on Card 1 is arranged in two left justified columns. Card 6 also uses only type but the type is arranged into the five treatment categories with one or two sentences of

explanatory text. The sentences are left justified and include bold type to emphasize negative associations with each treatment category. This card has the greatest amount of text of all of the six cards. Because cards 1 and 6 use only text for communication, they will be discussed as a group.

Figure 1 Tested decision aid cards [8], from upper left: Card 1, Card 2, Card 3, Card 4, Card 5, and Card 6.

Cards 2, 3, 4, and 5 use a combination of typography, color, symbols, charts, and graphs in their designs. The graphics on each card vary with regard to how read or decode the information. The statistical information, seen on Card 2, uses dots to represent certain affected categories and forces the user to make visual comparisons and associations. In the case of the icons on Card 3, the information is quickly understood as a concept. On Card 4, a chart requires the user to interpret frequency data and combine it with a short verbal explanation. Whereas the visual Likert-type scale on Card 5 requires the user to make positional associations with regard to positive or negative changes from a neutral position in the center of the line. Because cards 2, 3, 4, and 5 use both text and graphics to communicate their information, they will be discussed as a group.

2.2. Focus Group Study

A series of focus groups were conducted to analyze the DAs in terms of their use of design variables such as color, typography, material usage, information hierarchy, visual density, and visual complexity. The results from these focus groups were used to create emotional property lists for the survey. Through the focus group study and a literature review fourteen word pairs with twenty-eight words were selected for the final survey tool. The focus groups were recruited on campus by word of mouth and participants were encouraged to recruit people from their own social group (friends, relatives, colleagues). Because most medical decisions are not made in isolation, but in collaboration with a trusted social circle, these groups were designed to reflect this social dynamic.

2.3. Survey

The survey was designed to use the actual DAs for the testing so that participants could hold them and physically experience them. Survey responses were recorded directly into an online survey tool for analysis. After the survey, the data was analyzed to determine what words were most predicative of positive or negative responses. Participants' voices were recorded to examine how their language and verbal expressions supported the survey data. The survey was conducted over approximately a five-month period and one hundred seven people participated. The survey data was analyzed using SPSS.

It was designed to rank the six DAs on a scale of one to six, with one being the least associated with a word and six being the most associated with a word for each of the twenty-eight words in the survey. The word pairs that did not show correlation with their opposite word were eliminated from this research. The word pairs that were eliminated from the data due to a lack of correlation were: efficient, time consuming, empowering, manipulative, educational, and instructional (table 1).

Table 1 Word Pairs [9]

Word 1	Word 2	Sig. (2-tailed)	Pearson correlation
Healthy	Sickly	.010	-.916*
Trustful	Deceitful	.010	-.915*
Interesting	Boring	.001	-.974*
Clear	Ambiguous	.030	-.855*
Relevant	Useless	.011	-.913*
Simple	Complicated	.004	-.948**
Efficient	Time Consuming	.203	-.605
Empowering	Manipulative	.864	-.091
Functional	Useless	.001	-.980**
Personal	Generic	.060	-.793
Educational	Instructional	.186	-.624
Comforting	Frightening	.011	-.914*
Happy	Sad	.002	-.968**
Comprehensive	Limited	.000	-.984**

* correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) ** correlation is significant at the .01 level (2-tailed)

3. Findings and Discussion

The cards were evaluated based on the survey results and an expert assessment of their visual design elements. Table 2 shows mean values for each of the 22 words from the survey. These values were then tested with regard

to their validity based on their correlation with their score on the opposing word from the survey. The significant positive words were then subjected to factor analysis to determine if they measure the same concept. Reliability testing was done to validate the scales created. Using these scales emotional property of each word were ranked by demographic information.

Table 2. Mean Value [10] (N= 107)

	Card 1	Card 2	Card 3	Card 4	Card 5	Card 6
healthy	2.73	2.67	4.83	4.43	3.54	2.86
sickly	3.66	4.29	2.72	3.14	3.44	3.71
trustful	2.64	2.6	3.83	4.48	3.03	4.45
deceitful	3.91	4.57	2.8	2.89	3.94	2.9
interesting	1.85	3.53	4.68	4.21	3.87	2.86
boring	4.8	3.44	2.34	3.25	3.05	2.34
clear	3.35	1.94	4.35	3.95	3.44	3.96
ambiguous	3.98	4.77	3.17	2.98	3.82	2.31
relevant	2.65	3.09	4.38	4.42	3.04	3.43
useless	4.51	4.35	2.51	2.7	3.96	2.91
simple	4.33	2.07	4.75	3.46	3.44	2.79
complicated	2.49	5.19	2.45	3.6	3.68	3.61
functional	2.4	2.43	4.98	4.64	3.08	3.87
useless	4.51	4.35	2.51	2.7	3.96	2.91
personal	2.1	2.68	4.84	3.98	3.96	3.44
generic	4.95	3.22	2.89	3.08	3.03	3.82
comfortable	2.68	2.4	4.99	4.46	3.6	2.88
frightening	3.51	4.58	2.22	3.05	3.5	4.14
happy	2.72	3.21	5.46	4.12	3.68	1.83
sad	3.68	3.99	2.09	3.11	3.5	4.65
comprehensive	1.84	2.89	3.89	4.77	3.09	4.54
limited	5.29	3.76	3.11	2.47	3.84	2.44

3.1 Respondents Demographic Information

Tables 3 and 4 show demographic information. The majority of participants were English speakers and Caucasian. Thirty-eight percent of the participants were male and sixty-two percent of the participants in the survey were female. Those with an above college graduate level of education accounted for approximately sixty-six percent of the respondents.

Table 3 Percentage of Survey Respondents based on Gender, Language, and Ethnicity

Gender (N=107)				Language (n=106)				Ethnicity (n=105)			
Male		Female		English		Non-English		Caucasian		Non-Caucasian	
No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
40	37.38	67	62.62	98	92.45	8	7.55	88	83.81	17	16.19

Table 4 Percentage of Survey Respondents based on Education and Income

Education (n=107)						Income (n=92)							
High School		College		Above College		Under \$24,999		\$25,000-\$49,999		\$50,000-\$149,000		above \$150,000	
No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
4	3.74	32	27.91	71	66.36	31	33.70	11	11.96	43	47.74	9	7.61

3.2. Cards that Use Text and Graphics for Communication

3.2.1 Card 2

Of the six cards, Card 2 has the highest percentage of visual information on it. The title bar is a deep gold color with the words “Low Blood Sugar” and, below in a second line and in a smaller point size, the word, “Hypoglycemia.” Both lines of text are written in black. The information on the card uses a combination of grey, yellow, and red dots as symbols to visually represent percentages associated with risk. There are a total of 35 words of information on the card. The five treatment categories are in the same weight and point size, however the symbolic data in the form of dots is dramatically different from the treatment categories in weight. This creates some visual discord; however the overall appearance of the layout is highly compartmentalized and structured. This DA was rated most highly for the following words: complicated, ambiguous, frightening, and deceitful. Males rank this card higher in trust than females (table 5). People with lower levels of education find this more comfortable and comprehensive and younger people find this card more interesting and comprehensive (table 6). This card has the highest visual density and the many symbols and colors make this card hard to comprehend.

3.2.2 Card 3

Card 3 has a moderate quantity of visual information. The title bar is a yellow green color with the words “Daily Routine” written in black. The information on the card uses a combination of text for the treatment categories and symbols for food, medicine, and injections. There are a total of 20 words of information on the card. The five treatment categories are in the same weight and point size, however some categories have more text or symbols than others. This creates some imbalance between the treatment categories; however the overall appearance of the layout is visually engaging because of the colored icons and structured due to the text and visual delimiters.

This card is most highly associated with the following words: happy, comforting, functional, personal, healthy, interesting, and simple. All of these highly associated words are positive in nature. Females prefer this card in all categories; specifically trust, functional, happy and comprehensive (table 5). People ages 24-55 rank this card higher in six positive categories (table 6). This card has a well-balanced proportion of words to symbols and uses color effectively to create interesting visual relationships.

3.2.3 Card 4

Card 4 has a large quantity of visual information on it. The title bar is a dark green color with the words “Daily Sugar Testing” and, below in a second line and in a smaller point size, the word, “(Monitoring).” Both lines of text are written in white. The information on the card uses a combination of text for the treatment categories and a chart with red dots to indicate monitoring frequency and a 2-4 line block of explanatory text. There are a total of 56 words of information on the card. The printed content utilizes only 32% of the space. The five treatment categories are in the same weight and point size, however some of the monitoring frequency charts have more red dots than others. The overall appearance of the layout is somewhat visually engaging because of the charts and red dots. This card appears structured due to the justification of the text and charts and it appears compartmentalized due to the use of visual delimiters.

This card is most highly associated with the following words: comprehensive, trustful, and relevant (table 5). Females rank this card higher in healthy than do males This card has an average level visual density. The meaning of the color red varies across the series. The use of symbols and explanatory text in a clear column layout improve the comprehension of the information.

3.2.4 Card 5

Card 5 has a moderate quantity of visual information on it. The title bar is a dark purple color with the words “Weight Change” written in white. The information on the card uses a combination of text for the treatment categories and a horizontal bar that is comprised of closely positioned grey boxes with white plus or minus signs arranged going out from a neutral center point. Starting in the center, the boxes are colored in a range from light blue to magenta to indicate weight gain and in a range from light blue to dark blue to show weight loss. There are a total of 28 words of information on the card. The five treatment categories are in the same weight and point size. The overall appearance of the layout is somewhat visually engaging due to the color transitions in the horizontal bars. This card appears very compartmentalized due to the use of the horizontal bars as visual delimiters.

This card was not ranked most highly in any positive or negative category. People with higher levels of education find this more functional. This card has an average visual density and the color palette is more subtle in nature. The use of repetition and balance creates visual interest or eye movement across the card.

3.3. Cards that Use Only Text for Communication

3.3.1 Card 1

Of the six cards, Card 1 has the lowest percentage of visual information on it. The title bar is a deep red color with the words “Blood Sugar” and, below in a second line and in a smaller point size, the words, “(A1c Reduction).” Both lines of text are written in white. The information on the card uses no symbols and only 13 words of drug names and associated percentages. The five treatment categories are in the same weight and point size, however the numerical data (percentages) are inconsistent in size and weight.

This card is most highly associated with the following words: boring, useless, generic, and limited. Males find this card significantly more happy than females. Males rank this card higher than females in most categories (table 5). People with lower levels of education find this more comfortable (table 6). This card has the lowest visual density and the red and black color palette is masculine in nature.

3.3.2 Card 6

Card 6 has the highest quantity of visual information on it. The title bar is a dark magenta color with the words “Side Affects” written in white. The information on the card uses only text for the treatment categories and for the explanation of the side affects. In addition, certain words such as nausea, indigestion, diarrhea, fluid retention (edema), and rash have been somewhat randomly emphasized in the text through the use of a bold weight text. There are a total of 131 words of information on the card. The five treatment categories are in the same weight

and point size. The overall appearance of the layout is complicated due to the relatively large quantity of text. This card appears very full and text-heavy.

This card is most highly associated with the word sad. Native English speakers rank this more highly in relevance than non-native speakers. People ages 18-23 find this card more trustful, relevant, and comfortable. Higher incomes rank more interesting (table 6). This card has a high visual density and the largest amount of text.

3.4 Gender and Emotional Properties

There are several common emotional and experiential properties found between male and female respondents (table 5). Both female and male respondents perceive card 2 as complicated, sickly, deceitful, and ambiguous. All these words are associated with negative emotional properties. While, both female and male perceive card 3 as functional, personal, interesting, manageable, happy, and healthy. All these words are associated with positive experiences and emotional properties. Male respondents perceive card 6 as comprehensive, trustful; while at the same time these male respondents also perceived it as frightening and sad. Female respondents on the other hand, perceive card 4 as comprehensive and trustful. Both female and male respondents perceive card 6 as least ambiguous and happy.

Table 5. Gender Preferences with regard to emotional properties associated with DA cards.

	Most Preferred		Least Preferred	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
healthy	3	3	2	6
sickly	2	2	3	3
trustful	6	4	1	2
deceitful	2	2	4	3
interesting	3	3	2	1
boring	1	1	3	3
clear	4	3	2	2
ambiguous	2	2	6	6
relevant	4	3	1	1
useless	2	1	4	3
simple	1	3	2	2
complicated	2	2	1	3
functional	3	3	1	2
useless	2	1	4	3
personal	3	3	1	1
generic	1	1	4	3
comfortable	4	3	2	2
frightening	6	2	3	3
happy	3	3	6	6
sad	6	6	3	3
comprehensive	6	4	1	1
limited	1	1	6	4

3.5 Age and Emotional Properties

All age groups perceive card 3 as happy, card 6 as sad, and card 2 as complicated (table 6). The age 18 to 24 group perceive card 4 as comprehensive, functional, personal, relevant, comfortable, and manageable. All these words are associated with positive emotional and experiential properties. While the age 24 to 55 group perceives

card 3 as functional, personal, relevant, clear, comfortable, interesting, and manageable. All these words are associated with positive emotional and experiential properties. The age 55 and above group perceives card 6 as functional and card 3 as comprehensive, personal, and interesting. Card 6, the most text heavy card, was perceived as trustful from age 18 to 55 while card 4, a card with a balance of text and graphical information, was perceived as trustful from age 55 and above.

Table 6. Age preferences with regard to emotional properties associated with DA cards.

	18-23		24-55		55+	
	Most Preferred	Least Preferred	Most Preferred	Least Preferred	Most Preferred	Least Preferred
healthy	3	1	3	2	4	2
sickly	6	3	2	3	2	4
trustful	6	3	6	2	4	1
deceitful	2	4	2	3	1	4
interesting	2	1	3	1	3	1
boring	1	3	1	3	1	3
clear	6	2	3	2	3	2
ambiguous	2	4	2	6	2	6
relevant	4	5	3	1	4	1
useless	5	6	1	3	1	4
simple	1	2	3	2	1	2
complicated	2	1	2	3	2	3
functional	4	1	3	2	6	1
useless	5	6	1	3	1	4
personal	4	1	3	1	3	1
generic	1	5	1	3	1	5
comfortable	4	2	3	2	4	2
frightening	6	3	2	3	2	3
happy	3	6	3	6	3	6
sad	3	6	3	6	3	6
comprehensive	4	1	4	1	3	2
limited	1	6	1	4	1	6

3.6 Income and Emotional Properties

All income groups (table 8) perceive card 2 as complicated and least clear, card 6 as trustful and sad, and card 3 as efficient, healthy, and happy. Those in the income category “Less than \$25,000” and “\$150,000+” perceive card 4 as comprehensive and functional. Higher income group, “\$150,000+”, perceives card 6 as relevant, trustful, and clear. This group’s positive emotional properties are more likely associated with card 4.

Table 8. Income with regard to emotional properties associated with DA cards

	Less than \$25,000		\$25,000-49,000		50,000-\$149,999		\$150,000+	
	Most Preferred	Least Preferred	Most Preferred	Least Preferred	Most Preferred	Least Preferred	Most Preferred	Least Preferred
healthy	3	6	3	2	3	2	3	1
sickly	2	3	6	3	2	3	2	6
trustful	6	5	6	1	4	2	4,6	2
deceitful	2	4	2	4	2	3	1	6
interesting	3	1	4	1	3	1	3	1
boring	1	3	6	3	1	3	6	2

clear	6	2	3	2	3	2	1,4,6	2
ambiguous	2	6	2	4	2	6	6	1
relevant	4	5	3	1	4	1	3,6	1
useless	2	3	2	3	1	4	5	6
simple	3	2	1	2	3	2	4	2
complicated	2	1	2	3	2	3	2	1
functional	4	2	3	1	3	1	4	5
useless	2	3	2	3	1	4	5	6
personal	3	1	3	2	3	1	3	2
generic	1	5	1	3	1	3	1	6,4
comfortable	3	2	3	2	3	2	4	1
frightening	2	3	6	3	2	3	2	3,5
happy	3	6	3	6	3	6	3	6
sad	6	3	6	3	6	3	6	5
comprehensive	4	1	6	1	6	1	4	1
limited	1	4	1	6	1	4	1	6

4. Conclusions

In general, several of the cards were commonly found to have the same associations by both males and females. Other cards showed differences in preferences based on gender, age, or income. Card 1 was particularly more highly associated with negative words, while Card 3 was more highly associated with positive words. Cards with more sophisticated use of color and a balance between symbols and explanatory text seem to receive higher and more positive associations in general. DAs with more complicated graphics were seen as interesting if the graphics were easy to understand, but were perceived as more negative if the viewer was required to do more involved processing of the visual information. Text could be perceived as either a good thing or a bad thing. Large amounts of text were seen both as sad and trustful. Smaller amounts of text were seen as generic or boring. From a visual design standpoint, the combination of text and graphics is the most effective in creating a positive emotional and experiential response from the greatest number of people. The text should be sufficient to communicate the information effectively and the graphics should be easy to decipher and have enough color to create visual interest. A clear grid structure also seems to have a more positive response.

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